

INFLUENCES OF PROCESS PARAMETERS ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HYBRID SHEET METAL-FRP-COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED BY PREPREG PRESS TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The aim of lightweight design is to reduce the mass of a product or structure while keeping the material properties on a constant level. With this approach it is possible to decrease the energy consumption and emissions of vehicles, for example. For a few years in the field of automotive lightweight design a trend towards tailored and/or multi-material respectively hybrid structures is obvious.

Tailored components can be realised by the use of high-strength metal alloys like 22MnB5 and modern process technologies like partial press hardening or partial inductive hardening. Multi-material structures characterise a combination of two or more materials on a component level. A well-known example is the so called “Erlanger Beam”. Here, a sheet metal hat structure is combined with a polymer ribbing to improve the mechanical properties while the weight decreases up to 30 %. In contrast to multi-material systems hybrid materials or structures are defined as a combination of different materials on a material level. That means, i. e. sheet metal and fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) are extensively joined together usually by adhesive bonding. The prepreg press technology is one approach to manufacture hybrid structures. Hybrid components include a lightweight potential up to 50 % compared to sheet metal structures corresponding to boundary conditions like the load situation or geometrical constraints.

Current research work at the Chair for Automotive Lightweight Construction at the University of Paderborn concentrates on the investigation of hybrid materials and their processing. In particular, new manufacturing processes like the prepreg press technology are developed in order to enhance the attractiveness and availability of hybrid components for automotive mass production. This includes, for example, trimming process chains, reducing cycle times and thus a reduction of process steps and costs. In addition, various combinations of hybrid materials are examined based on material and component tests.

This paper will show basic technological investigations in the field of prepreg press technology. In this process the prepreg is directly pressed onto a formed sheet metal structure and pre-cured for about 90 to 120 s. The post-curing is realised in an anyway downstream cataphoretic dip painting process. The bonding is realised by the use of the epoxy resin as an adhesive. With expected cycle times of less than five minutes the developed approach for manufacturing locally reinforced components is one possibility to solve the challenges of high-volume manufacturing in the field of CFRP. In the available paper the optimisation of process parameters (pressure, time, and temperature) will be discussed. The focus is to identify influences i. e. on the mechanical properties, e. g. (bending) strength or adhesion properties. The results are adequate process windows for the prepreg press technology regarding varying boundary conditions or different aims (costs vs. properties/quality).

1 INTRODUCTION

Lightweight design in industrial applications like automotive engineering is one approach to meet the objectives of climate protection [1]. For example, 100 kg less vehicle mass would reduce the CO₂ emissions of about 8.5 g/km or respectively the fuel consumption up to 0.3 l/100 km. Nevertheless the

average weight of automobiles increased over the past years mainly because of safety and comfort requirements. To take further steps in this context, new innovative and holistic approaches are needed.

Lightweight design has become a core competence especially in the automotive industry in the past years. A weight reduction of a construction can be realised in different ways, for example by using superior metal alloys or by substituting metal by FRP. Nowadays a main trend is the utilisation of fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) for automotive applications. Materials like carbon (CFRP) or glass fibre reinforced plastics (GFRP) offer excellent specific mechanical properties [1], [2], which are significantly higher than those of steel, aluminium or magnesium alloys. A high specific modulus and strength are required for loadbearing structures in the automotive, aerospace or energy sector for example [4], [5]. Consequently, FRP offer a large weight saving potential for lightweight construction. At the moment FRP-structures are predominantly used for high-priced vehicles, prototypes, premium products or race cars [4], [6].

Research works have shown that the use of FRP results in significant functional and economic benefits. These benefits range from increased strength and durability features to weight reduction and lower fuel consumption. Research results also show the improvement of structural vehicle crashworthiness by using FRP in specific automobile structures as collapsible absorbers of crash energy [7–9]. Main challenges for the automotive industry are to integrate FRP into existing processes, to reduce high costs of processing these materials and manufacturing FRP-structures. Thus, the competitiveness of these structures depends on reducing costs for example by optimising technologies that enable simple and robust manufacturing processes or shorter lead times [6], [10], [11]. To improve the utilisation of material it is favourable to use high-strength, but also high-priced materials like CFRP as local reinforcements in sheet metal structures. These reinforcements can be applied to high loaded areas for example of a hat section or a b-pillar [12], [13]. Such hybrid combinations of CFRP and metals are increasingly used in the automotive and aerospace industry, but also in general mechanical engineering [12]. With the use of this construction technique an aluminium section reinforced with adhesively bonded CFRP could be realised 33 % lighter than a mere aluminium optimised structure [14].

Hybrid structures consist for example of formed sheet metal structures and (local) FRP-patches [15], [16]. The wall thickness of the sheet metal can be reduced, which leads to a decreasing weight. Highly loaded areas are reinforced with FRP to their expected loading [12]. Another hybrid structure can be found in the combination of Sheet Moulding Compounds and FRP Prepregs [11]. Such tailored structures do not only bear a high potential for lightweight design but also show an optimised use of the expensive FRP materials, which finally leads to cost-optimised lightweight constructions. Amongst others press hardened steels can be used as sheet metals. Hybrid components can easily be integrated into existing processes of vehicle production, because their metallic surface enables the use of conventional joining technologies like spot welding or clinching. The integration into existing body constructions is also possible.

2 MANUFACTURING OF HYBRID COMPOSITES

Prepreg press technology is one approach that can be applied to the high-volume production of hybrid structural automotive parts [17]. According to specific requirements two different process routes are available (Figure 1). The indirect prepreg press technology can be divided up into six main parts. First of all, prepregs (pre-impregnated, semi-finished fibre products) are produced continuously on special machines and shipped on coils. The layer structure is configured on the basis of the loads that are expected on the component, for example a b-pillar. The laminate is cut to match the subsequent geometry of the structure. In the second step, the prepregs are handled by a robot. Afterwards, the prepreg stacks are formed and cured in a heated mould. An adhesive bonding process takes place in the fourth step, followed by the fifth step, where a formed sheet-metal-structure and the FRP component are combined and cured. The curing of the adhesive and, depending on the level of pre-curing in step three, the epoxy resin is also realised in a heated mould or oven process. The finished hybrid structures can be handled and stacked. A final post-curing of the components can be performed by a downstream cataphoretic dip painting process.

Figure 1: Process steps for indirect and direct prepreg press technology to produce hybrid automotive structural parts, for example a b-pillar

By the use of the direct prepreg press technology the process steps can be reduced from six to four steps. The idea is to cut out the separate bonding process. This can be realised by the use of the epoxy resin as an adhesive or by the use of an adhesive film, which is directly applied on the prepreg layer in the first step. After stacking, cutting and handling (steps 1-2) the laminate a pre-formed steel structure is placed in a heated steel tool. The tailored prepreg is applied to the steel structure in an automated handling operation. The prepreg is then pressed onto the sheet metal by a heated punch. Since the epoxy resin functions as an adhesive, the sheet metal and CFRP are bonded together in this third step, too. After a pre-curing period of about 90 to 120 s, depending on the thickness of the prepreg, the hybrid

component can be removed by a robot and stacked. The post-curing of the components again takes place during a downstream cathaphoretic painting process.

The closed mould employed in prepreg press technology can be identified as a bottleneck, and the high cycle time reduces the suitability of prepreg press technology for high-volume production. Relevant process parameters correlate directly with the cycle time for the press process. Hence, the process parameters ought to permit short cycle times and good mechanical properties at one and the same time. The influence of different parameters is discussed below.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND METHOD

For purposes of investigating the prepreg press process, use was made of epoxy-resin prepreps with nine layers of carbon fibre non-crimp fabric (unidirectional). The bidirectional structure of plies was $(90/0/0/90/0/90/0/0/90)^\circ$. The matrix resin employed was an SGL of type E201 and, for the steel component, a S235JR alloy with a thickness of $t = 2$ mm was selected. The use of the matrix resin as an adhesive for bonding the sheet metal and the CFRP makes an additional joining process superfluous.

In order to investigate influences of relevant parameters on the process and on the mechanical properties of the hybrid laminates, test plates were manufactured. In a further step specimens were cut out from these laminates according to the specified tests. The geometry of the tested three-point-bending specimens are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Geometry of the tested three-point-bending specimens and illustration of the deflection curve

For three-point-bending tests the bending stress σ_{max} and strain ε_{max} of the outer fibre were calculated with the following equations (1) and (2):

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{F \cdot \frac{l}{2} \cdot E_{1,2} \cdot z_{max}}{E_1 \cdot I_{y1} + E_2 \cdot I_{y2}} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_{max} = \frac{z_{max}}{\rho} = \frac{z_{max}}{r} = -\frac{8 \cdot w_s \cdot z_{max}}{l^2 + 16 \cdot w_s^2} \quad (2)$$

where F is the maximum force, l the distance between the supports, E the Young's modulus of the sheet metal (E_1) and the CFRP (E_2), z_{max} the maximum distance between the outer fibre and the neutral axis, I the second moment of area, w_s the displacement in y-direction, ρ the reciprocal of the curve of the beam and r the radius of the deformed beam respectively. The radius can be set out in the general form of the equation of a circle for a three-point bending setup (see also Figure 2):

$$r^2 = (x - x_M)^2 + (y - y_M)^2. \quad (3)$$

Introducing the known geometric constraints, the radius can be expressed by equation (4):

$$r = -\frac{l^2 + 16 \cdot w_s^2}{8 \cdot w_s} \quad (4)$$

4 PROCESS PARAMETER STUDIES

The process parameter studies aimed for a suitable process window, that realises both a high laminate and component quality at minimum cycle times. As relevant process parameters for the prepreg press technology occur the pre-curing time, the temperature and the pressure. Here, especially the pre-curing time is a very important process parameter for achieving short cycle times. The process parameters were studied *ceteris paribus*. First, hybrid test laminates were manufactured with previously defined parameters. Second, the test laminates were post-cured in a simulated cataphoretic dip painting process (Oven process, 30 minutes at 180 °C). Then, three-point-bending specimens were cut out from the plates and tested afterwards.

In Figure 3 the results of three-point-bending tests for different combinations of temperatures and pre-curing times are illustrated at constant consolidation pressure of 0.3 MPa. It shows the values for the maximum bending stress achieving a plateau of about 1050 MPa for pre-curing times above 60 s and temperatures above 160 °C. The values decrease at temperatures higher than about 190 °C. A longer pre-curing time does not lead to higher bending stresses, when the maximum plateau is reached.

Figure 3: Results of three-point-bending tests for different combinations of temperatures and pre-curing times

The results for three-point-bending-tests for different combinations of temperatures and pressures at a constant pre-curing time of 120 s are shown in Figure 4. The best mechanical performance can be identified for pressures of 0.3 to 0.4 MPa and pre-curing temperatures around 180 °C. Here, maximum bending stresses of about 1050 MPa occur.

Figure 4: Results of three-point-bending tests for different combinations of temperatures and pressures

The failure of the three-point bending specimens is characterised primarily by forced fracture in the centre, where the bending load is applied. Around this area, several delaminations were detected in 90° layers or in the interface between 0° and 90° layers. The sheet metal had undergone plastic deformation.

To sum up, a minimum pre-curing time of between 90 and 120 s is realistic for a prepreg-thickness of 2 mm and the use of standard epoxy resins. Allowance should be made for a safety factor due to the varying tool temperature in a real manufacturing process.

Figure 5 shows several micro sections and fibre volume contents of samples manufactured with different process parameters. Especially the pressure has a decisive influence on the fibre volume ratio. A pressure between 0.2 and 0.4 MPa achieves the provided fibre volume fraction of about 60 %. The pre-curing time and the temperature have nearly no influence on this characteristic. Nevertheless the quality of the laminate finds an optimum at 180 °C and 90 s.

Summarising, optimal process parameters for the prepreg press process were found: the temperature for low cycle times should be about 180 °C, the pressure should be between 0.3 and 0.4 MPa and the time should be above 90 s. These values depend on influence factors such as the layer thickness, the materials or the textile semi-finished component.

			0.1 MPa	0.2 MPa	0.4 MPa	0.6 MPa
160 °C	60 s	Micro-section				
		FVC*	$\varphi = 55.96 \%$	$\varphi = 57.30 \%$	$\varphi = 58.87 \%$	$\varphi = 67.27 \%$
	90 s	Micro-section				
		FVC*	$\varphi = 56.77 \%$	$\varphi = 60.40 \%$	$\varphi = 60.62 \%$	$\varphi = 64.74 \%$
180 °C	60 s	Micro-section				
		FVC*	$\varphi = 55.09 \%$	$\varphi = 62.95 \%$	$\varphi = 64.83 \%$	$\varphi = 65.73 \%$
	90 s	Micro-section				
		FVC*	$\varphi = 55.62 \%$	$\varphi = 56.77 \%$	$\varphi = 63.26 \%$	$\varphi = 67.85 \%$
200 °C	60 s	Micro-section				
		FVC*	$\varphi = 56.56 \%$	$\varphi = 55.61 \%$	$\varphi = 62.64 \%$	$\varphi = 65.62 \%$
	90 s	Micro-section				
		FVC*	$\varphi = 55.70 \%$	$\varphi = 55.56 \%$	$\varphi = 61.80 \%$	$\varphi = 66.40 \%$

*FVC - Fiber volume content (Mean value of five measurement points)

Figure 5: Micro sections and fibre volume content of different samples [18]

An adequate adhesive bonding technology for the prepreg press process could be implemented in the semi-finished product as a laminate layer (cf. Figure 1, step 1). This would make a separate adhesive bonding superfluous. For the technical realisation an adhesive film, which is applied on top of the prepreg stack, or the epoxy resin matrix itself could be used as an adhesive.

Several investigations have been performed, for example shear tensile or peeling tests [19]. For quasistatic shear tensile tests the epoxy resin shows a suitable mechanical performance with a bond strength of up to 24.2 MPa on a degreased steel surface (Figure 6). The fibre orientation of the boundary layer had an enormous influence on the properties of the joint. Samples with fibre orientation vertical (90°) to the direction of loading (0°) showed the highest strength. The elastic matrix material dominated the mechanical properties close to the boundary layer. In general the elastic properties, especially the

stiffness, of the matrix material determines the properties of the ply, when the fibre direction is orthogonal to the load according to the model of springs in series systems. [20], [21]. The elasticity of the fibers is about 60 to 70 times as high as the stiffness of the epoxy matrix. The fibres only bear a small part of the load. The laminate can thus absorb local tension peaks like a bond line. Samples with fibres orientated parallel to the loading, in the contacted layer, failed with 75% of the load applied [22]. The stiffness of the layer with fibre orientation in direction of the load is dominated by the material properties of the fibres like in a parallel connection of springs [20], [21]. The difference in (max.) strain of the carbon fibres in fibre direction to the sheet metal is probably too big.

The inhomogeneous structure of CFRP is reflected in the properties of the joint. The special properties of these materials need to be taken into account in the design of hybrid structures in order to achieve the intended properties of the compound.

Figure 6: Influence of the fibre orientation of the contacted layer on the bond strength [23]

5 INVESTIGATIONS ON AND CONCEPTS FOR THE MANUFACTURING PROCESS

Substantial demands to implement hybrid structures into automotive applications are adequate approaches for mass production. Several investigations aimed for the consolidation and curing process of the prepregs. In addition a test setup was developed to study the whole process chain and estimate cycle times of the manufacturing process of hybrid structures by prepreg press technology. In Figure 7 this test setup is illustrated. A pneumatic cylinder is fixed at a linear slide. At defined positions a locking is provided to perform an operation, for example the loading of prepregs by a vacuum gripper. The other stations were stacking of tailored prepregs and formed sheet metal structures, infrared pre-heating, forming tool and stacking of finished hybrid structures.

At the beginning of the process the carrying paper had to be removed manually. The subsequent manufacturing process could be realised within a cycle time of 30 s. Thereto, a time of 30 to 60 s had to be added for a pre-heating of the prepregs if necessary. With a pre-heating the formability of the prepregs can be improved, for example when complex geometries have to be manufactured. The pre-curing in the closed mould was between 90 and 180 s. Summarising, this leads to a complete cycle time between 150 and 270 s per part.

Figure 7: Test setup for investigations on the cycle times of the prepreg press process

Based on these results three process concepts were developed (Figure 8). The first concept includes linked hydraulic presses. A handling robot inserts formed sheet metal structures and tailored prepreps into a heated mould (cf. [13]). In order to reduce the cycle times, the mould can be realised as a multiple tool. The next step is the use of autonomous press devices instead of hydraulic presses, which reduces invest costs and enhances the flexibility. In the shown example a handling robot loads six devices, which results in a reduction of the cycle time for a hybrid component to about 30 s. The last process concept works with circulating press devices and represents a further evolution of concept two. Depending on the number of press devices a cycle time of about 15 s is theoretically possible.

Figure 8: Different process concepts for the large series manufacturing of hybrid components

6 CONCLUSIONS

Hybrid structures consisting of sheet metal and fibre reinforced plastics offer a major potential for lightweight design in the automotive industry. Prepreg press technology permits a significant reduction in the number of process steps as well as in the process time. With this manufacturing technique semi-finished FRP-products can be formed, cured and afterwards adhesively bonded with sheet metal structures (indirect process). By using prepreg press technology it is also possible to form CFRP prepreps directly onto steel structures. This process design allows cycle times to be significantly reduced

from over 10 minutes to less than 5 minutes. With advanced manufacturing processes a further significant reduction of cycle times is possible.

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